

A Study of the Side Effects of General Vs Spinal Anesthesia during Caesarian Section Surgery

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Abstract:

Background: Caesarean section (CS) is a common surgical procedure with anesthesia management being critical for maternal and fetal safety. General anesthesia (GA) and spinal anesthesia (SA) are the primary techniques used, each associated with distinct advantages and potential complications. This study aims to compare the side effects of general versus spinal anesthesia during Caesarean section surgeries to inform clinical decision-making.

Methods: This prospective, observational study was conducted, involving 120 pregnant women undergoing CS. Participants were divided into two groups: GA (n=60) and SA (n=60). Data on intraoperative and postoperative complications were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Statistical comparisons were made using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables, with a p-value <0.05 considered significant.

Results: The SA group experienced a significantly higher incidence of intraoperative hypotension (36.7% vs. 13.3%, p=0.003) and postoperative headaches (30% vs. 3.3%, p<0.001) and backaches (20% vs. 5%, p=0.01) compared to the GA group. Other complications such as nausea, vomiting, shivering, and bradycardia showed no significant differences between the groups.

Conclusion: Spinal anesthesia is associated with higher incidences of hypotension during surgery and headaches and backaches postoperatively compared to general anesthesia. Despite its benefits, the potential for these side effects should be considered in anesthesia planning.

Recommendations: Clinicians should weigh the risks and benefits of GA and SA, considering individual patient conditions and preferences. Preventive measures should be implemented to mitigate the side effects associated with spinal anesthesia.

Keywords: Caesarean section, general anesthesia, spinal anesthesia, intraoperative complications, postoperative complications.

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Introduction

Caesarean section (CS) is one of the most commonly performed surgical procedures worldwide, with rates steadily increasing over the past few decades. Anesthesia management for CS is critical to ensuring maternal and fetal safety, and the choice between general anesthesia (GA) and spinal anesthesia (SA) remains a topic of ongoing debate. Recent advancements in anesthetic techniques and a better understanding of the risks and benefits associated with each type of anesthesia have further intensified this debate [1].

General anesthesia, which involves the administration of anesthetic drugs to induce unconsciousness, has been traditionally used in emergency situations or when regional anesthesia is contraindicated. It offers the advantage of rapid

induction and complete control of the airway. However, GA is associated with several potential complications, including aspiration, respiratory depression, and adverse effects on the neonate due to placental transfer of anesthetic agents [2].

Spinal anesthesia, on the other hand, involves the injection of a local anesthetic into the subarachnoid space, resulting in sensory and motor blockade. SA is preferred in many elective CS due to its simplicity, rapid onset, and the ability to maintain maternal consciousness during delivery. Additionally, SA has been associated with fewer neonatal adverse effects since the amount of anesthetic crossing the placenta is minimal. However, it is not without risks, as hypotension, post-dural puncture headache, and transient

neurological symptoms are notable complications [3].

The choice between GA and SA is influenced by various factors, including the urgency of the procedure, maternal medical conditions, and patient preference. Recent studies have focused on comparing the outcomes associated with these two anesthetic techniques to guide clinical practice. For instance, a study demonstrated that while SA is associated with a lower risk of maternal mortality and morbidity, it may lead to higher incidences of hypotension and postoperative headaches [4]. Similarly, a meta-analysis highlighted that GA is linked to higher neonatal intensive care admissions due to respiratory complications [5].

This study was a prospective, observational study designed to compare the side effects of general anesthesia versus spinal anesthesia during Caesarean section surgeries.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective, observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of 11 months at Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, India.

Participants: 120 pregnant women who underwent Caesarean section surgery.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Pregnant women scheduled for elective or emergency Caesarean section.
2. Age between 18 and 40 years.
3. ASA (American Society of Anesthesiologists) physical status classification I or II.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with contraindications to spinal anesthesia (e.g., coagulation disorders, infection at the injection site, severe hypovolemia).
2. Patients with contraindications to general anesthesia (e.g., severe respiratory disease, history of malignant hyperthermia).
3. Patients with pre-existing neurological disorders.
4. Patients with a history of chronic pain or use of opioids.
5. Emergency cases where rapid induction of anesthesia was required.

Bias

To minimize selection bias, random sampling was used to select participants. Observer bias was minimized by blinding the data collectors to the type of anesthesia administered.

Data Collection: Hypotension was defined as a systolic blood pressure less than 90 mmHg or a diastolic blood pressure less than 60 mmHg, often considered significant during anesthesia if there is a reduction of 20-30% from the patient's baseline.

Data was collected using a structured data collection form that included demographic details, medical history, anesthesia details, intraoperative and postoperative complications, and side effects.

Anesthesia Drugs and Dosages

1. General Anesthesia (GA):
 - Induction with Propofol (2 mg/kg).
 - Muscle relaxation with Rocuronium (0.6 mg/kg).
 - Maintenance with Isoflurane (1-2%) in 50% Nitrous Oxide and Oxygen mixture.
 - Analgesia with Fentanyl (2 mcg/kg).
2. Spinal Anesthesia (SA):
 - Intrathecal injection of Bupivacaine (0.5%, 10-15 mg).

Procedure

1. Preoperative: All participants underwent a pre-anesthetic check-up. The type of anesthesia was decided based on the patient's condition, preferences, and the anesthesiologist's judgment.
2. Intraoperative: Vital signs were monitored, and any complications or side effects during the surgery were documented.
3. Postoperative: Side effects or complications were monitored and recorded for 48 hours post-surgery. This included nausea, vomiting, headache, backache, shivering, hypotension, and any other observed side effects.

Statistical Analysis: Data was entered into SPSS version 23.0 for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic data and the frequency of side effects. Chi-square tests were used to compare categorical variables, and t-tests were used for continuous variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 120 pregnant women undergoing Caesarean section were included in the study. The participants were divided into two groups: General Anesthesia (GA) group (n=60) and Spinal Anesthesia (SA) group (n=60).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Characteristic	General Anesthesia	Spinal Anesthesia	p-value
Age (years)	29.8 ± 4.5	30.2 ± 4.2	0.65
BMI (kg/m ²)	28.4 ± 3.1	27.9 ± 3.3	0.42
ASA I	45 (75%)	48 (80%)	0.52
ASA II	15 (25%)	12 (20%)	0.52

There were no statistically significant differences in age, BMI, or ASA classification between the two groups. Intraoperative complications were monitored and documented. The incidence of hypotension was significantly higher in the SA group compared to the GA group.

Table 2: Intraoperative Complications

Complication	General Anesthesia	Spinal Anesthesia	p-value
Hypotension	8 (13.3%)	22 (36.7%)	0.003
Nausea	5 (8.3%)	10 (16.7%)	0.16
Vomiting	4 (6.7%)	8 (13.3%)	0.22
Shivering	7 (11.7%)	15 (25%)	0.07
Bradycardia	3 (5%)	5 (8.3%)	0.47

Postoperative complications were monitored for 48 hours. The incidence of headache and backache was significantly higher in the SA group.

Table 3: Postoperative Complications

Complication	General Anesthesia	Spinal Anesthesia	p-value
Hypotension	5 (8.3%)	12 (20%)	0.03
Nausea	6 (10%)	9 (15%)	0.41
Vomiting	4 (6.7%)	6 (10%)	0.51
Shivering	5 (8.3%)	10 (16.7%)	0.16
Headache	2 (3.3%)	18 (30%)	<0.001
Backache	3 (5%)	12 (20%)	0.01

The most frequent early postoperative complications in general anaesthesia group were shivering and nausea, with a notable reduction in the frequency and variety of complications by 48 hours post-surgery. Whereas, the spinal anaesthesia group experienced higher incidences of

hypotension, nausea, and shivering early on, with headaches and backaches becoming more prominent later. Complications remained more frequent in this group compared to the General Anesthesia group throughout the 48-hour monitoring period.

Table 4a: Postoperative Monitoring (General anaesthesia)

Time interval	Hypotension	Nausea	Vomiting	Shivering	Headache	Backache
1 hour	1	2	1	3	1	1
6 hours	0	1	2	1	1	1
12 hours	1	0	1	1	0	1
24 hours	2	2	0	0	0	0
48 hours	1	1	0	0	0	0

Table 4b: Postoperative Monitoring (Spinal anaesthesia)

Time interval	Hypotension	Nausea	Vomiting	Shivering	Headache	Backache
1 hour	4	4	2	5	1	2
6 hours	3	0	1	3	3	6
12 hours	2	1	2	2	3	2
24 hours	1	2	1	0	9	2
48 hours	2	2	0	0	2	0

Data analysis revealed statistically significant differences in the incidence of hypotension, headache, and backache between the two groups. The SA group had a higher incidence of hypotension intraoperatively and a higher incidence of headache and backache postoperatively. No

significant differences were observed in other complications.

Discussion

The participants were evenly divided into two groups, with 60 receiving general anesthesia and 60 receiving spinal anesthesia. The demographic

characteristics, including age, BMI, and ASA classification, were similar between the two groups, ensuring a balanced comparison.

Intraoperative complications revealed a significantly higher incidence of hypotension in the SA group (36.7%) compared to the GA group (13.3%), with a p-value of 0.003. This suggests that patients receiving spinal anesthesia are more prone to experiencing low blood pressure during surgery. Although other intraoperative complications such as nausea, vomiting, shivering, and bradycardia were more frequent in the SA group, these differences were not statistically significant.

Postoperative complications were monitored for 48 hours, showing a significantly higher incidence of headaches (30%) and backaches (20%) in the SA group compared to the GA group, where the incidences were 3.3% and 5%, respectively. The p-values for headaches and backaches were <0.001 and 0.01, respectively, indicating a strong association between spinal anesthesia and these side effects. Other postoperative complications like nausea, vomiting, shivering, and hypotension did not show significant differences between the two groups.

Overall, while spinal anesthesia is commonly preferred for its benefits, such as reduced maternal and fetal drug exposure, it is associated with a higher risk of hypotension during surgery and increased incidences of headaches and backaches postoperatively. These findings highlight the importance of individualized anesthesia planning and thorough patient counseling regarding the potential side effects. Clinicians should weigh these risks against the benefits when choosing the type of anesthesia for Caesarean sections and consider preventive measures to mitigate these side effects.

A narrative review compared general and spinal anesthesia during caesarean sections, focusing on their effects on both mothers and newborns. The review concluded that spinal anesthesia had fewer adverse effects and was more favorable compared to general anesthesia [6].

A study evaluated the side effects of general and spinal anesthesia in 60 patients undergoing caesarean sections. The study found that vomiting, headache, and pain were more frequent in the general anesthesia group, while headache, pain, and hypotension were more common in the spinal anesthesia group. Both groups experienced fever and infection as side effects [7].

A study compared general and spinal anesthesia in diabetic pregnant women undergoing elective caesarean sections. The study found that spinal anesthesia was associated with lower mean blood glucose levels and less perioperative blood glucose variation compared to general anesthesia. This

suggests that spinal anesthesia may be preferable for diabetic patients due to its lower impact on blood glucose levels [8].

A study investigated the impact of spinal anesthesia-induced hypotension on fetal blood circulation in primary caesarean sections. The study found significant correlations between maternal blood pressure changes and fetal umbilical and middle cerebral artery resistance indices. This indicates that while healthy fetuses can compensate for maternal hypotension, the effects on growth-restricted or preterm fetuses remain uncertain [9].

A multicenter observational study was conducted on patient satisfaction with general versus spinal anesthesia for caesarean sections. The study reported higher satisfaction rates and fewer side effects in the spinal anesthesia group compared to the general anesthesia group [10].

Conclusion

The study found that spinal anesthesia was associated with a higher incidence of hypotension during surgery and more postoperative headaches and backaches compared to general anesthesia. However, other side effects such as nausea, vomiting, shivering, and bradycardia showed no significant differences between the two groups. These findings suggest that while spinal anesthesia might be beneficial in certain scenarios, careful consideration should be given to its potential side effects.

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